

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16414345

Board Governance Mechanism And Sustainability Disclosures Quality Of Nigerian Listed Companies

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ABSTRACT

Research on Sustainability Reporting in most emerging economics is still grey considering the scanty investigations that have been conducted so far. Hence there is a dearth literature regarding Sustainability practice. in emerging markets including Nigeria. This study investigates the effect of board governance mechanisms (board communication, board independence, board size, and board meetings) on the Sustainability Disclosures Quality (SDQ) of the Top 100 Nigerian listed firms. The study utilizes a longitudinal sample of 498 firm year observations of financial and non-financial companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange for the period 2017 to 2021. The results of the panel regression that board communication (overlapping directorship), board independence, and board size positively and significantly influenced the SDQ of the sampled firm. While board meetings recorded a negative and significant influence though, the positive association indicates an improvement in the Sustainability disclosure of listed firms, the extent or quality of such disclosure is still low and calls for (overlapping). The improvement could be achieved via effective board and necessary regulatory changes in the SEC and NGX. Therefore, the study has policy implications for regulator, in terms of strengthening compliance with the guide sustainability reporting guide (CRI): the companies regarding the role of the boards in ensuring corporate sustainable disclosure practice; and the government, and other stakeholders as it has to do in maintaining or increasing the pressure to enhance, sustainability commitments of firms. The study bridged literature gaps by offering new insights and empirical evidence on the role of board communication, board independence, board size, and board meetings in the Sustainability disclosure of Nigerian large firms. The study recommends that listed companies should take board communication, board independence, and board size seriously as they are crucial determinants of the level of sustainability disclosure. Also, the study recommends that the frequency of board meeting should be optimized to see that it could influence Sustainability disclosure positively.

Keywords: board communication, board independence, board size, board meetings and sustainability disclosures quality

INTRODUCTION

The concept 'Sustainability' was defined in a report issued in 1987 (Brundtland Report) by the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) entitled "Our Common Future" with emphasis on a process of change in which the exploitation of resources, the direction of investments, the orientation of technological development, and institutional change are made consistent with the future as well as present needs" (WCED, 1987, p. 9). The report, therefore officially defined sustainable development as development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet their own needs" (WCED, 1987).

Sustainability reporting is therefore a global phenomenon in business practices (Chikwendu. Okafor. & Jesuwunmi, 2019) that emerging economies can afford to avoid if sustainable development must be achieved (Elaigwu et al., 2020). It is capable of increasing both the short and long-term performance of companies as well as establishing corporate legitimacy for business organizations (Tiamivu & Oyekunle, 2021). Adhipradana and Daljono (2014) opined that existing and potential investors can determine the well-being of firms in terms of their performance using sustainability reporting without necessarily looking at the annual reports. Hence, several business failures, for example, Enron, WorldCom, and others in recent history have been blamed on unethical practices and manipulative tendencies in corporate reporting of firms which has queried or cast doubt on the appropriateness of sustainable business behaviors (Skouloudis et al., 2014). To ameliorate such an act of opportunism is the call for sustainability disclosure (reporting) practices that could reinstate stakeholder trust, legitimize companies' operations, project a good corporate image, and enhance long-term firm performance. Achieving this entails effective board governance in terms of the board of directors' responsibilities in controlling and monitoring corporate performance and information disclosures as documented by extant literature (Ahmed Haji, 2013; Baba & Abdul-manaf, 2017; Cliikwendu et al 2019; Haniffa Cook, 2005; Katmon et al., 2019; Osazuwa et al., 2017; Osemene & Fagbemi, 2019; Sanusi & Sanusi, 2019; Zahid et al., 2020). The present study, therefore, employs board attributes like board communication, board independence, board size, and board meeting to examine the level of sustainability disclosure in Nigeria.

1.3 Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to examine the relationship between board governance mechanisms and the sustainability disclosure quality of Nigerian listed companies. The specific objectives are as follows:

- i. To evaluate the relationship between board communication and sustainability disclosure quality of listed companies in Nigeria.
- ii. To investigate the relationship between board independence and sustainability disclosures quality of listed companies in Nigeria.
- iii. To determine the relationship between board size and sustainability disclosure quality of listed companies in Nigeria.
- iv. To examine the relationship between board meetings and sustainability disclosure quality listed companies in Nigeria.

1.4 Statement Hypotheses

To enable the study to achieve its objectives, the following constitute the null hypotheses to be tested:

- H₀₁: Board communication has no significant relationship with the sustainability disclosure quality of listed companies in Nigeria.
- H₀₂: Board independence has no significant relationship with the sustainability disclosure quality of listed companies in Nigeria,
- H₀₃: Board size has no significant relationship with the sustainability disclosure quality of listed companies in Nigeria.
- H₀₄: Board meetings have no significant relationship with the sustainability disclosure quality of listed companies in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

The study did a conceptual review as it bothers on sustainability practices as enshrined in the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs; and the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) as shown in the following sections.

2.1.1 Sustainability Disclosure (Reporting)

The concept of sustainable development, an initiative of the United Nations came into the limelight in 1987 through a report known as the Brundtland report at the United Nations conference lagged "Agenda 21" in support of sustainable development in Rio de Janeiro. As of 1992, a period of fewer than five years, 178 countries had adopted a comprehensive action plan tagged "Agenda 21" (UN Conference on Environment and Development. 1992). The quest for sustainability reporting was borne out (societal concern over the sustainability of the human-economic system where the population's exponential growth rate poses a great danger to the biophysical carrying capacity of the planetary ecosystem (American Accounting Association).

Sometimes, the word sustainability reporting is used interchangeably with corporate social responsibility. However, studies have shown that corporate social responsibility is used by companies in the advanced world to secure their reputation -while sustainability reporting creates endless opportunities for emerging economies to thrive. For instance, Dyduch and Krasodomska (2017) opined that the global financial crisis of 2008 was responsible for the increase in the number of demands for more detailed and comprehensive reports in the form of sustainability or corporate social responsibility concepts to restore investors' and consumers' confidence in the markets.

On a contrary perspective, Lys et al. (2015) opined that corporate attainability is not just an interest in the environment, corporate social responsibility, or strategic philanthropy, hut an awareness of the interests of stakeholders in ensuring economic viability while maintaining a sustainable environment that is socially responsible. The discussion of the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) in 1987 conceptualized sustainability practices and indicates that the future is quite important as the present time (WCED, 1987). The importance of the future is portrayed in the definition of sustainable development given by the WCED. The definition was anchored on the principle that our present actions should not be detrimental to the future concerning the Economic, Environmental, and Social (EES) options (I Ikini'ton, 1997; WCED, 1987). The report officially states that sustainable development (sustainability) "is the development that meets the present needs without denying the future generations the ability to meet their own needs (WCED, 1987). Sustainability is not a new phenomenon, even though trending, as extant literature, has shown its existence for quite a long time (Ong, 2016; Ong & Djajadikena. 2018). Sustainability practice is considered an advanced stage of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) practice (Djajadikerta. 2017; Ong, 2016). Sustainability as defined by WCED, gained acceptance by several previous research on sustainability practices. The definition refers to sustainability or CSR as a calculation towards sustainable development which brings forth tin idea of sustainability reporting (Deegan. 2013; Guenther et al., 2006; Guthric & Aheyseker, 2006). in furtherance of this, a non-profit organization called the GRI defined sustainability reporting as "reporting on how an organization contributes or aims to contribute in the future, to the improvement or deterioration of economic, environmental and social conditions, developments, and trends at the local, regional or global level" (GR1. 2015. P. 17). This organization (the GR1) emphatically suggests that sustainability concept be widely presented in such a way that involves discussing the performance of the organization in the context of the limits and demands placed on environmental or social resources at the sector, local, regional, or global Level" (GRI, 2015).

2.1.3 Board Governance Mechanisms

Board governance modernisms in this study refer to the corporate governance issues associated with the board of directors. Generally, corporate governance is taken to be the relationship that subsists between the stakeholders and the management of firms (Millar et al 2005). Dahya et al. (1996) considered corporate governance to the process of control through which corporate organizations are managed by the managers who are in turn accountable to the various stakeholders of firms.. The broader definition of corporate governance states that "it is the system of laws, regulations, institutions, markets, contracts, and corporate policies and procedues (such as the internal control system, policy manuals, and budgets) that

direct and influence the actions of the top-level decisions makers (shareholders, boards, and executives) in the corporations" (Brickley & Zimmerman, 2010, p.236; Shanmugam, 2017). This portrays the idea of using governance elements to make firms engage in 'green or sustainable practices to enhance green environment via resource conservation (C'ooke, 2015).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.2 Stakeholder Theory

The stakeholder theory posits that companies are responsible not only to their shareholders but to other stakeholders that surround the company's existence (Freeman, 1984). Stakeholder theory is mostly employed in previous research for explaining the reasons firms disclose information relating to sustainability practices (Sener et al., 2016). The theory bothers on the fact that for firms to keep surviving, it becomes pertinent that such firms must manage appropriately their relationship with their specific stakeholders (Freeman et al. 2004). That is, the stakeholder theory focuses more on the group identified as stakeholders of the company that deserves the attention of the management. Hence, previous investigations indicate how the stakeholder orientation of companies could positively affect the performance of the organization (Sener et al., 2016).

A stakeholder is defined by Freeman in 1984 as "any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organization's objectives" (Freeman, 1984, p.16). Freeman emphasized that firms' response to stakeholders' expectations and the maintenance of cordial relationships avail the company of a competitive advantage for survival. In consonance with Freeman (1984)'s basic perception of the stakeholder perspective, the stakeholder theory constitutes the ethical or moral, or normative branch that explains the concept of corporate environmental accounting (Deegan & Bhmquist, 2006). The normative perspective posits that "The stakeholders of companies have the right to fair treatment. This is notwithstanding the benefits accruing from stakeholder management to the firm regarding performance. Therefore, the managers' management of the companies must be for the benefit of the entire stakeholders of the organization.

This perspective is extended to the fact that all stakeholders have the right to information concerning the relative impact of the company on them positively or negatively. Such an impact could be probably via pollution, community sponsorship, and provision of employment, safety initiatives, and others. This is devoid of the stakeholders' inability to directly impact the survival of the organization" (Burhan & Rahmanli, 2012). Besides, Clarkson (1995) categorized the stakeholders of firms into two groups- that is, the primary and secondary stakeholders. The primary stakeholders are those that the absence of their continued participation with the firm could lead to the firm's failure in terms of survival as a going concern (Clarkson, 1995). In other words, there exists a high level of interdependence between the firms and such stakeholders to the extent that the lack of such interdependence might halt the firms' survival. Such primary stakeholders are the shareholders or investors, creditors, employees, customers, suppliers, and even the public in the form of the government and the communities. (Clarkson, 1995). While the secondary stakeholders are the ones that influence or are influenced by the companies' activities but are irrelevant or not essential for the company's survival, for instance, the media and other special interest groups (Clarkson, 1995).

2.3 Empirical Review

Elaigwu et al. (2020) in their work titled "board governance mechanisms and sustainability reporting quality: A theoretical framework", conceptually examine the association between board governance mechanisms and sustainability reporting quality in Malaysia. The effect of governance attributes like board diversity, board communication, board integrity, and political connections was conceptually investigated regarding sustainability reporting. The method adopted by this study is the review of previous literature on sustainability reporting practices. To gain insight into drawing a proposition

regarding the relationship between board attributes and sustainability reporting quality practices of PLC's in Malaysia. Through this method, the study generally verifies the sustainability reporting quality of firms and how it is influenced by board attributes. Based on the insight from the reviewed past investigations, the study concludes in its proposition that board communication (overlapping membership) and the other board governance elements examined have a positive effect on sustainability reporting quality based on multiple theories. The study has practical implications for the companies, regulators, government, and other stakeholders their policy considerations and investment decisions. The study recommends empirical study to re-investigate sustainability reporting quality employing the variables used in this study and other board attributes to enhance the sustainability of the findings.

Velte (2018) in a work titled "do overlapping audit and compensation committee memberships contribute to better financial reporting"? The study examines overlapping membership in the audit and compensation committees and its impact on financial reporting. The analysis covers a sample of German firms listed on the Deutscher Aktienindex (DAX). 'Tec DAX' (for mid-sized companies), and 'MDAX' (technology companies) for the business years 2010-2016 (426 firm-year observations). The researcher hand-collected data on OMAC and other governance variables from annual, corporate governance, and sustainability reports. Correlation and regression analyses were conducted to evaluate the link between two overlapping variables and financial reporting quality. While the first overlapping variable (proportion of audit committee members who also sit on the compensation committee) contributes positively to financial reporting, no significant results were found for the second overlapping variable (the existence of an independent financial expert as an overlapping member). The main result holds for robustness checks and has major implications in the German two-tier system. The study recommends that overlapping directorship or membership is key to financial reporting as the proportion of overlapping members is linked with an increased financial reporting quality. The authors explain this result as the effect of knowledge spillovers from overlapping membership, which is useful to the audit committee's monitoring duties concerning the financial reporting process.

Fernandez. Mendel et al., (2017) in research titled "Monitoring by busy and overlap directors: an examination of executive remuneration and financial reporting quality¹", examine the influence of board directorships and boards' committee memberships on three supervisory outcomes: executive remuneration, external auditor opinion, and earnings management. The study uses a panel of 122 non-financial companies listed on the Spanish Stock Exchange over the period 2004-2011. The results show that firms with busy directors offer low executive remuneration and present a low probability of a qualified audit opinion. Furthermore, the results indicate that firms with overlapped directors exhibit a higher probability of receiving a qualified audit opinion. Additionally, we find evidence that the overcommitment effects of busy and overlapping directors are more evident for large firms. Overall, our findings suggest that busy (overlap) directors are beneficial (detrimental) to the monitoring capability of the board in the Spanish context.

Aliyu (2019) studied board characteristics and corporate environmental reporting in Nigeria. The purpose of the study is to investigate the relationship between corporate governance variables. Namely, board size, board independence, board meeting (BM) risk management committee composition, and CER in Nigeria. The study utilized the data obtained from the annual reports of 24 non-financial public listed companies in the Nigeria Stock Exchange comprising three sectors, namely, industrial goods, natural resources, and oil & gas for the period of 2011-2015. The model of the study is theoretically based on agency theory. In analyzing data, the study utilized panel data analysis. Based on the Hausman test, the random effect model was used to examine the effect of predictors on CER. The result indicates a positive and significant relationship between board independence and CER. The study provides suggestions for future research and several recommendations for regulators, government, and accounting, professional bodies regarding the role of board attributes as key determinants of environmental disclosures.

Odoemchim and Okafor (2018) study the influence of corporate governance on the environmental disclosure of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria in 2015. The study specifically investigates the effect of board independence, board meeting, environmental committee, audit committee independence, board size, firm size, auditor type (Big4), and industry membership on environmental disclosure. The population of the study is made up of the 109 listed non-financial enterprises in the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSF) with 86 firms selected as the sample size, the results of the OLS regression show that board independence is statistically significant. Among the three company attributes used only firm size significantly influence the quality of overall environmental disclosure of the sample companies. Auditor type "big 4" (Ernest Young, Deloitte, KPMG, and PwC) and industry membership show insignificant relation to environmental disclosure. The findings indicate that the level of environmental disclosure of non financial companies in Nigeria is quite insufficient at an average of 10.5 percent. It is not surprising that environmentally sensitive industries and auditor type had no significant influence on the extent of environmental disclosure. This buttresses the point that the environment the companies operate in is institutionally and Legal K weak. Hence it calls for improvement in environmental law and implementation as well as harmonized environmental reporting infrastructure and standards to aid comparison.

Olbegbu et. al. (2018) conducted an investigation titled "Corporate board characteristics and environmental disclosure quality: Evidence from South Africa (integrated reporting) and Nigeria (traditional reporting). The study aimed to compare the influence of corporate board characteristics like board size, board independence, and board meetings on the extent of environmental disclosure quality of listed firms in two leading emerging economies in South Africa (integrated reporting framework) and Nigeria (traditional reporting framework). The sample comprised 303 firms including environmentally sensitive companies purposively selected for content analysis study in South Africa (213) and Nigeria (91). The study used both descriptive, multivariate and regression models to comparatively analyze the differences in corporate board characteristics as determinants of the extent of their environmental disclosure quality. The results reveal a more significant positive association between board independence and environmental disclosure in South Africa and a less relevant association in Nigeria. Also, the results support that board independence arrangements may serve as bonding mechanisms in weak reporting environments, suggesting a substitutive relationship between board independence and the regulatory framework. The results are consistent with stakeholder theory agency theory; institutional theory, and legitimacy theory suggesting that strong independent members of the board with auditing experience may reduce information asymmetry. Our findings will be helpful for policymakers and other regulators who are interested in environmental impact reporting.

Shahali and Ye (2018) in China studied corporate social responsibility disclosure and corporate governance: empirical insights on the neo-institutional framework from 2008 to 2015. The study specifically examined the effect of state ownership, institutional ownership, block ownership, board size, board composition, and CEO duality on CSR disclosure. The population consists of firms listed on the Shanghai Stock Exchange (SSE) from which a sample of 1166 companies was selected. The empirical results based on panel data-generalized least squares estimations divulge that state ownership and block ownership are negative predictors of CSR disclosure, while institutional ownership, the board size, and board composition positively affect CSR disclosure in Chinese listed firms. The results fail to find a significant impact of CEO duality on CSR disclosure. The empirical findings of this study suggest practical guidelines for policymakers, government, and corporations in their drive against CSR concerns and recommend that board size should be taken seriously as it matters in sustainability practice.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Rest-arch Design

The study adopts an *ex-post facto* research design as the data extracted from firms' annual reports; are historic. The study is equally longitudinal as it covers different firms for various years.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of the study is the entire companies (161) listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group between 2017 and 2021 which includes all the sectors of the economy.

3.3 Sample Size of the Study

The sample consists of the Top 100 firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group from 2017 to 2021 (see Appendix B). This period is chosen to enable the researcher to observe how the past dispensation of President Muhammadu Buhari had shown concern for the issue of sustainability practice and to see the effect of the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance (NCCG) reform in 2018 which has the issue of sustainability on its top list (Ozili, 2021) as well as for the sake of using more current data. The consideration of large firms (top 100) is based on market capitalization and consistent with previous investigations which consider the use of larger firms as a common practice in sustainability reporting research (Kuhn et al., 2018; Loza Adau. 2020; Sierra-Garcia et al., 2018; Zainal, 2017). Equally, previous investigations document that larger firms are more exposed to public visibility with more impact on society as well as the necessity of their legitimization (Kuhn et al., 2018; Thong & Thong, 1984; Zainal, 2013, 2017). Moreover, larger firms have more likelihood of employing sustainability reporting in responding to public pressure (Zainal, 2013).

3.4 Sources of Data and Collection Procedure

This study employed secondary data covering the period from 2017 to 2021. The annual reports of listed companies were obtained from the NGX website and constitute the main source of data. Therefore, the data collection instrument is content analysis. The company's annual report is widely accepted as a statutory report by different stakeholders (Vergoossen, 1993) as a medium of sustainability disclosure (Harte & Owen 1991). Hence, the annual report can be easily assessed compared to other media sources (Suttipun & Stanton, 2012) and is regularly published (Wilmshurst A. Frost. 2000). Data concerning sustainability disclosure quality were hand-picked from the sustainability reporting section of the annual reports using content analysis as mentioned earlier. Also, data relating to board governance variables such as board communication, board independence, board size, and board meeting as well as other financial variables were hand-picked from the companies' annual reports. For instance, from sources like corporate governance statements, chairman's, statements, director's reports, board's profile, and the statement of financial position for the year 2021.

3.5 Model Specification

This study estimates the following panel regression model to be able to test the hypothesis, on the relationship between the variables of interest. The modeling of the relationship between board communication, board independence, board size, board meeting, and sustainability disclosure quality agrees with the framework of the underpinning theories. The model specification captures the independent variables and the dependent. Specifically, the functional linear regression equation is presented below:

$SDQ_{it} = f(BCOM_{it} + B1NDEP_{it} + BSIZE_{it} + BMEET_{it})$ The study therefore, estimates the following model (multivariate panel data regression) to be able to test the formulated hypotheses on the relationship between board governance mechanisms and sustainability disclosure quality.

$$SDQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BCOM_{it} + \beta_2 B1NDEP_{it} + \beta_3 BSIZE_{it} + \beta_4 BMEET_{it} + \beta_5 CSISE_{it} + \beta_6 LEV_{it} + \beta_7 ROE_{it} + \beta_8 INDDUM_{it} + \beta_9 YEARDUM_{it} + \dots \dots \dots \text{Model}$$

3.6 Technique of Data Analysis

The study used a panel regression analysis. Several statistical techniques are available to derive accurate conclusions from data. The study analyzes the data by employing descriptive statistics, correlation as well as panel regression analysis. The descriptive analysis was employed as the statistical tool for checking the mean, minimum, maximum as well as standard deviation. To obtain the appropriate model, diagnostic tests were conducted to check for multi-collinearity, heteroskedasticity, and autocorrelation (Allard & Murphy, 1975; Wooldridge, 2002).

3.6.1 Panel Regression Analysis

The research model developed above expresses the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable by employing a linear regression model that is presented in the form of an equation. The ordinary least square estimator is the commonly employed method for obtaining a line of best fit. But, because of the limitations of the ordinary least square estimation method, especially relating to the heterogeneity issue, the method may not be the best linear and unbiased estimator for the present study. Consequently, the panel data regression method is taken to be more appropriate (Asterion & Hall, 2007) and used by this study for testing the association between the variables of interest. The panel data regression model is chosen as a result of the benefits accruing to its use. For instance, it controls for individual heterogeneity, data are more informative and have less correlation among variables. Also, it has more degree of freedom as well as more efficiency (Baltagi, 2005). Panel data regression has other benefits such as being efficient in studying the dynamics of changes as well as having a better ability to identify and equally measure effects that cannot easily be detected when using complete cross-sectional data. Similarly, panel data regression is good at testing more complicated behavioral models and ameliorates or eliminates bias as a result of aggregation over individuals and firms. In addition, the pooling effect assumption renders it feasible for obtaining a good estimate and the omitted variables, which may lead to a biased estimate in a single regression (Asteriou & Hall, 2007). Based on these features, the present study employs the Static Panel Estimation method.

3.6.2 The Static Panel Data Estimation Model

There are three main regression models under static panel data econometric analysis. These include the Pooled Effects (PE), the Fixed Effect (FE) as well as the Random Effect (RE) Models. The principal difference among these models lies in the treatment of individual effects (D. Gujarati, 2006). The study observed the individual effect which will capture the heterogeneity among individuals. However, the primary decision of the panel regression model is the determination of the appropriate model for estimation purposes between the Pooled Effect regression model and the Fixed Effect/Random Effect models. To enable this study to determine the appropriate model, the fixed effect for the FE and the Lagrange Multiplier test which was introduced by Breusch and Pagan (1980) to choose between the PE model and FE/RE-model were used. The Lagrange multiplier test observes the presence of an unobserved effect in the fixed effect models and the decision criterion is that if the value calculated is greater than the critical value, the null hypothesis is then rejected. Thereby, rendering the FE/RE model more appropriate.

In furthering the process, in a situation where the PE model becomes inappropriate, a further decision is needed to choose between the RE and FE models. To distinguish the appropriate model between the two calls for a test of whether the individual effect correlates with the independent variables. To achieve this, the study employed Hausman's (1978) specification test which observes the difference between the RE and the FE estimates. If according to the null hypothesis, the error terms do not correlate with the independent variables, it means, rejecting the null hypothesis which signifies the appropriateness of the FE model.

3.6.3 Diagnostic Test

Despite the good benefits accruing to panel data stated in section 3.6.1 above, the method has its drawbacks. As such, to avoid having unreliable results, the study ran diagnostic tests to check for the absence of the entire likely experimental problems. The tests conducted are the heteroscedasticity,

autocorrelation, and multicollinearity tests. There are various ways of checking for the existence of heteroscedasticity as well as the rules that guide its detection (D. Gujarati. 2006). But the choice of which test to employ is a function of the statistical package chosen for the analysis. Hence the present study used panel data analysis by employing Stata Statistical Software, the method deemed appropriate is the Modified Wald test for Groupwise heteroscedasticity (Greene, 2003). In the presence of heteroscedasticity issues, a corrective action using the white heteroscedasticity-corrected standard errors which are otherwise known as the robust standard error could be employed (Gujarati & Porter 2009; Long & Whitlington, 1994).

Autocorrelation constitutes another issue to consider under the panel data type of analysis. This is a result of the issue relating to the correlation between the distance term and the observation in time and space (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). Its presence will result in a consistent but inefficient estimate in terms of the regression coefficients as well as a biased standard error. Autocorrelation could be detected by employing the method called the Wooldridge test for autocorrelation. The test involves, ascertaining the significance of the null hypothesis to show that there is no presence of idiosyncratic error (i.e. error that occurs due to incorrect measurements) in the linear panel data model. A significant F-value signifies the presence of autocorrelation. The Random Effect model could be used to correct the autocorrelation error. However, because the present study is a short panel, the autocorrelation issue might not be a threat (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). In the same vein, the data multicollinearity issue may not constitute a serious threat in a panel data model hence, the model itself has the capability of reducing its effect (Baltagi. 2005). Nonetheless, it is a common practice to check to ensure that the regressors are not highly correlated to avoid bias-variance that will lead to unreliable estimates (Gujarati & Porter; 2009). The common diagnostic test that could be employed for the detection of multicollinearity is the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and the Correlation Matrix.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.2 below presents the results of the descriptive analysis of the sustainability disclosure quality (SDQ) model from 2017 to 2021.

Table 4.2

Descriptive statistics for dependent, independent, and control variables from 2017 to 2020

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
SDQ	498	0.26	0.67	0	58
BCOMM	498	0.50	0.12	0.2	0.82
BINDEP	498	0.39	0.13	0.18	0.65
BFSIZE	498	9.06	2.04	4	17
BMEET	498	6.43	2.06	3	21
CSIZE'LOG	498	23.24	18.59	8.67	58.81
LEV	498	30.96	19.11	0.31	70
ROE	498	14.68	16.77	8.03	68.8

SDQ is sustainability disclosure quality, BINDEP represents board independence, BFSIZE is board size, BMEET represents board meetings. CSIZE stands for company size; LEV is leverage and ROE represent return on equity. The result shows a 26% mean value for SDQ with 0 as the minimum and 58% as the maximum value. This is though low but reveals an improvement in the sustainability disclosure level of listed firms in Nigeria which is consistent with prior literature (Ofogbu et al 2018; Sanusi and Sanusi, 2019). Board communication (overlapping directorship) has a mean of 50%, 2%, and 82% as minimum and maximum values. It means that overlapping directorship is a regular practice in this context. I he

average overlap is similar to the situations in the United States where 71% (on the higher side) of the audit, committee members sit on the compensation committees (Kalelkar, 2017), and in (Germany where the overlap is 34.5% (on a lower side) on (Velte, 2018). Board Independence (BINDER) has a mean value of 39% with a minimum value of 18% and a maximum of 65% which is similar to the work of Ofoegbu. Odoernelam & Okafor(2018). It indicates that the independence of the board is below average. The mean value 01 the board size (IJSIZE) is 9.06% with 4 as a minimum and 17 as a maximum which is consistent with previous studies (Odoernelam & Okafor. 20 1 8: N. P. Osazuwa et. al., 20 I7).

Further, board meeting (BMEBT) has an average value of 6.43 with 3 minimum numbers of meetings and a maximum of 21 which is in tandem with extent literature (Odoerneiam tt Okafor. 2018; Otbegbu ct al. 2018). Company size (CSIZE) valued in natural log has a mean of 23.24 while the total assets range from a minimum of 8.67 and a maximum of 58.81 which is as well in agreement with past investigations (Abdulsalam A'- Babangida, 2020). Leverage depicts a minimum of 31% and a maximum of 70% with a mean score of 30.96% which is comparable to the work of Manning el. al. (2019). Lastly, Return on Equity (ROE) has a mean value of 14.68% with a minimum value of 8.03% and a maximum of 68.8% which is equally consistent with past studios (Haniffa & Cooke, 2005; Manning. Braam. & Reimsbach. 2019; Abdulsalam & Babangida, 2020).

4.2 Correlation Matrix

Table 4.3 below indicates the results of the correlation matrix for the SDQ model from 2017 to 2021.

Table 4.3

Pearson Correlation Matrix

VARIABLES	SDQ	RCOMM	BDINDEP	BSIZE	BMEET	CSIZE	LEV	ROE
SDQ	1.000							
BCOMM	0.021	1.000						
BDINDEP	***().! 18*	-0.075	1.000					
BSIZE	s.094	-0.007.	**0.262	1.000				
BMEET	0.001	0.021	**0.458	**0.315	1.000			
CSIZE	***0.'048	0.026	**0.208	**0.244	' "0.497	1.000		
LEV	**0169	-0.011	**0.212	***0.261	***0.253	-K'0.245	1.000	
ROE	-0.030	***(). I21	**'-0.281	**'-0.254	***-0.307	*-0.251	**-	1.000

Note: Relationship is significant at * = p < 0.10, ** - p < 0.05, and *** = p < 0'.01. SDQ is sustainability disclosure quality BCOMM represents board Communication, BINDEP represents hoard independence BSIZE is board BMEET represents board meetings, CSIZE stands for company size: LEV is leverage and ROE represents return on equity.

As shown above, the study computes a correlation analysis for all the variables to explain the level of relationship (Asteriou & Hall, 2007). A correlation that is not beyond 0.8 shows the absence of in Multi-collinearity problems (Gujarati. l'W5). The coefficient of correlation in this study is between -0,307 and 0.496 which is within the acceptable region. Hence the rule of thumb for the detection of multi-collinearity is if the correlation is significantly more than 0.80 (Corlett & Aigner 1972: Gujarat! & Porter, 2004: Gujarati, 1995). Table 4.2 presents the results of the Pearson correlation matrix. The rt suits generally suggest the absence of the problem of multi-collinearity hence there is no high correlation in all the relationships and the variables are mostly statistically significant. The absence of multi-collinearity is equally confirmed by the result of' the Variance Inflation Factor (VIH) as shown in Table 4.3 below.

4.3 Diagnostic test Results

Like other estimation methods (e.g., time series or cross-sectional data), panel data requires some diagnostic tests to check how suitable is the panel data models. Generally unlike the case of multiple regression models in which several assumptions are to be fulfilled to guarantee the reliability of the

results, panel data models are based on the techniques of the Generalized Least Squares (GLS) equation which is taken as transformed variables of the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) and invariably has already fulfilled the OLS assumptions (Greene, 2002; Gujarati, 2003). Moreover, the panel model is of the assumption that the disturbance terms are of homoscedastic variances and constant serial correlations via random individual effects (Baltagi, 2005).

Further, the normality and linearity assumptions do not constitute a threat (Gujarati, Porter, 2004) to the results of this study based on the following reasons. In the first instance, the assumptions of the standard least square do not apply in the panel data model. Secondly, the continuous variables have been converted into either log or ratio forms (Hair et al 2010). Lastly, for large sample sizes, the deviation from normality does not amount to a reasonable difference in the analysis (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2008).

4.4 Panel Regression Analysis

Panel regression begins with choosing between pooled, random, and fixed effect models as demonstrated in the following section.

4.4.1 Pooled Model versus Random Effect Model

The panel data analysis begins with the researcher establishing that the RE model is significant and not zero (Baltagi, 2005), which is an indication of the presence of an unobserved effect in the model (Wooldridge, 2002). The absence of meeting these criteria renders the RE model inappropriate (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). The Lagrangian Multiplier is used to choose between the pooled and the RE models (Breusch & Pagan, 1980). The results of the Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier test for the SIX model indicate that the $\chi^2 = 17.62$ at a 0.0000 level of significance. The significant result means that the null hypothesis is rejected which indicates that the variance of the RE is not equal to zero. Therefore, the RE model is more appropriate for the SIX model.

4.4.2 Random Effect Vs Fixed Effect Models

The suitability of either the FE or the RE model is determined by the 1 Hausman specification test (Hausman, 1978) which compares the coefficients of the two models (Kealy et al., 2007). The null hypothesis is that there is no difference between the coefficients of the FE and the RE models. The result of the Hausman specification test shows that $\chi^2 = 15.37$ at the level of 0.0000 significance which means the RE model is more appropriate for the SDQ model. However, because of the presence of autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity, the Panel-corrected Standard Error (PCSEs) which is robust for these issues is used as the estimation technique appropriate for the SDQ model. This is consistent with the observations of past investigations that deemed the OLS an unfit estimator for such circumstances (Zhuang, Chang, & Lee, 2018; Katmon et al., 2019).

4.4.3 Regression Results for Sustainability Disclosure Quality

As mentioned earlier, because of the presence of autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity, the Panel-corrected Standard Error (PCSEs) is used as the estimation technique appropriate for the SDQ model following past literature (Zhuang et al 2018 Katmon et al., 2019). The R² value for the SDQ model shows that the increase in sustainability disclosure is 49% explainable by the independent variables. Overall, no findings of this study show an improvement in the quality of sustainability disclosure of firms in Nigeria. Table 4.7 presents the results of the Panel Corrected Standard Errors (PCSEs) for the SDQ model.

Table 4.7

Regression result for SDQ

VARIABLES	FE	PCSEs
BCOM'	0.14 (1.57)	•0.03 (1.86)**
BOARDIND	0.15 (2.08)**	0.55 (7.83)***
BFSIZE	0.00 (0.54)	0.00 (1.71)*
BMEET	0.01 (1.73)	-0.01 (-2.35)**
CS	2.71 (2.81)***	5.44 (3.99)***
LEV	0.00 (0.65)	0.00 (6.36)***
INDDUM	-0.00 (-0.911)	0.00 (1.04)***
YEARDUM	YES	YES
	YES	YES
	O.OK	0.38
JBQH	(2.18)***	(8.14)***
<i>Number of firms</i>	100	100
<i>Number of obs</i>	498	498
R ²		49%
Prob>ch2	0.000	0.000
<i>Panels</i>		homoskedastic:
<i>Autocorrelation</i>		no autocorrelation

4.4.4 Test of hypothesis

The study investigates the relationship between board governance mechanisms (board communication, board independence, board size, board meeting) and sustainability disclosure quality. Table -4.7 presents the regression results of the multiple regression analysis from 2016 to 2021 using Panel Corrected Standard Errors (PCSES) estimation techniques.

Result for H2

The PCSES regression results as shown in Table 4.7 indicates a positively significant ($P = 0.03$ ($p < 0.05$)) relationship between board communication and SDQ. Thereby rejecting the null hypothesis (H1) that states that there is no significant relationship between BOARd communication and SDQ. This means that overlapping directorship enhances the level of sustainability disclosures.

Result for H2

The PCSEs regression results show a positively significant ($P 0.15$, $p < 0.01$) relationship between board independence and sustainability disclosure. Thereby rejecting the null hypothesis (H2) that states that there is no significant relationship between board independence and SDQ. This means that an independent board enhances the level of sustainability disclosures.

Result of H3

The PCSI-s regression results portray a positive but weakly significant ($p 0.00$, $p < 0.1$) relationship between board size and SDQ. Thereby rejecting H3 that states that there is no significant relationship between board size and SDQ. There means that boards that re larger in terms of size increase the quality of sustainability disclosures.

Result for H4

The PCSEs regression result revealed a negatively significant ($P = -0.01$, $p < 0.05$) relationship between board meetings and SDQ. Thereby rejecting H4 that states that there is no significant relationship between board meetings and SDQ. This implies that the frequency of board meetings decreases sustainability disclosure quality.

Results of Control Variables

Table 4.7 also presents the results for the control variables. The result shows that the relationship between company size (CSIZE) and SDQ is highly significant and positive. This shows that the size of a company has a positive influence on the level of sustainability disclosures. The coefficient of leverage (LEV) is equally significant and positive in its association with SDQ. Likewise, the coefficient of return on equity (ROE) is significant and positive in its relationship with SDQ.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.2 Conclusion

The study examines the effect of board governance mechanisms on the sustainability disclosure quality of the Top 100 Nigerian listed companies. The empirical result reveals that board communication, board independences, and board size are important determinant factors for sustainability disclosure quality. Despite the positive association between these variables SDQ, the level or extent of sustainability disclosures in Nigeria needs much improvement as is still low as indicated by the descriptive statistics. Based on the findings of the study, more effort is needed to step up the sustainability practice of listed firms in Nigeria. The findings enlighten regulators; policymakers like NGX and SEC to intensify efforts in ensuring that firms comply with the necessary sustainability reporting guide be it the GRI or the Nigerian Sustainability Reporting Guideline. That is a future regulator initiative might be required to re-enforce compliance. Thereby bringing the assumptions of the applicable theories to full accomplishment by reducing information asymmetry meeting the information needs of stakeholders, and promoting sustainable development via sustainability disclosure practices. In summary, if the board of directors takes board communication, board independence, and board size seriously, it positively affects corporate sustainability disclosures.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommends as follows:

- i. That board communication via overlapping directorship contributes a lot to the success of the board of directors as well as the entire company
- ii. That listed companies should take the issue of board independence seriously as it is one of the key determinants of sustainability disclosure practice.
- iii. Companies should beware of the size of the board as a larger board size is crucial for corporate sustainability practices,
- iv. Firms should beware that the frequency of board meetings be an optimal level as too many board meetings in a year may not amount to better sustainability practices.

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